

FACTORS INFLUENCING THE HABITUAL CONSUMPTION OF DISPOSABLE ELECTRONIC CIGARETTES AS PERCEIVED BY YOUNG ADULTS OF QUEZON CITY

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ABSTRACT

The prevalence of electronic cigarettes has grown rampant across recent years; establishing its demographic target among young adults and evolving within the market as a competitive trend capable of expanding its influences to launch newly improved variants — among these are Disposable Electronic Cigarettes. Promoted as a smoking cessation aid and embellished with desirable attributes, it became favorable among the youth, yet remained controversial due to vague health claims. This study aimed to assess factors that influence young adults' perceptions toward disposable electronic cigarettes and accompanying health risks upon habitual consumption. Designed as a quantitative descriptive research method, the chosen sampling design is non-probability purposive sampling to streamline respondents based on specific criteria. Using a survey platform, a self-made 35-item questionnaire was distributed to one hundred (100) identified respondents, aged 18-26 years old, within the vicinity of Quezon City. Accordingly, data was analyzed by statistical treatment, ranging from frequency and percentage, weighted mean to ANOVA test. Results of study indicated that factors according to demographic profile varied with significant differences, but majority of young adults chose to consume disposable electronic cigarette despite their awareness of the potential health risks. While in the perception on health risks of habitual consumption of disposable electronic cigarette, majority agreed it satisfies psychological demands. Accessibility and availability of the product in communities influenced habitual consumption, especially among male users. Recommendations include reinforcement in awareness of health promotion, such as participation in health-oriented programs, and the strict regulation of E-cigarette manufacturers advised for transparency of chemical properties.

Keywords: *Disposable Electronic Cigarette, Habitual Consumption, Young Adult, Health Risk, E-cigarette, Purposive Sampling, ANOVA, Quezon City*

INTRODUCTION

Acknowledged as a growing global health concern, the electronic cigarette became an epidemic phenomenon that has risen dramatically since its release; originally developed with the purpose to facilitate as a derivative smoking cessation aid. However, as it has exponentially established its prominence in the marketing industry, electronic cigarette transformed into a trend that expanded in size and variety to contend for profit and value against competing products, including tobacco cigarette – its primary subject of purpose.

The World Health Organization (2020) describes electronic cigarette as battery-powered device that heats liquid and turns into aerosol vapor for inhalation. Its basic components are comprised of an e-liquid, nicotine and flavoring, which are adeptly devised to enable customization of product preference and dosage control. Also, it is encompassed under the general category of *Electronic Nicotine Delivery System (ENDS)*, which refers to the umbrella term for non-combustible vaping products (Kotewar et al., 2023). In spite of the marketable success of electronic cigarette, however, it has become an area of concern for generating controversy among the public and experts due to its vague health claims.

Among the available variants of this product, disposable e-cigarette has grown distinctly popular among young adult consumers largely for the convenience, affordability, variety of flavor, advertisement and marketing packaging (Sese, 2023). Disposables are single-use devices that come prefilled with e-liquid and equipped built-in coil and battery which serves as an all-in-one package. This, in conjunction with the various influencing factors have significantly encouraged susceptible young adults to seek sensory experience and immediate satisfaction; potentially risking the development of habitual consumption and nicotine dependence - which subsequently leads to instigation of perceived health risks.

Furthermore, the Department of Health cited a Global Youth Tobacco Survey, in which it showcased the prevalence of usage expansion of disposable electronic cigarette among the Filipino youth. The presented data shows there is an 110% increase in consumption of the disposable electronic cigarettes in four years from 11.7% in 2015 into 24.6% in 2021 (Mocon-Ciraco, 2023). Additionally, based on a recent foreign study, Tattan-Birch (2022) stated an 18% increase of vapers who consume disposable electronic cigarettes from January 2021 to April 2022, are mostly pronounced among the young adults as its primary demographic. Case in point, the percentage of 18 years old vapers consuming disposable e-cigarette rose from 0.4% to 54.8%, amassing large usage among youth. Expectedly, the disposable e-cigarettes sold in the international market have nearly tripled in nicotine strength, quintupled in e-liquid capacity and significantly dropped in price by nearly 70% between 2017 and 2022 as stated in a Truth Initiative (2023) study.

Statistics are expected to progressively rise due to the leniency of regulation imposed by local government and non-compliance of e-cigarettes companies. The vaping epidemic in the Philippines exemplifies how commercial influences and government policies can

exacerbate health issues as it confronts the rising usage of electronic nicotine delivery system among Filipino youth (Sese, 2023). As aforementioned, habitual consumption of disposable electronic cigarettes can lead to dependence, in which the pleasure caused by the interaction of nicotine properties with the reward circuit motivates user to relyantly consume nicotine, despite the awareness of potential health risks (National Institute on Drug Abuse, 2018). Jankowski et al. (2019) further reinforced nicotine withdrawal effect can occur after cessation of chronic nicotine consumption. Exposure may have adverse effect with postulated risk, like impaired memory, substance abuse or poor performance. Excessive consumption can also develop lung complications. In February 2020, Centers for Disease Control and Prevention confirmed 2,807 cases of e-cigarette use associated lung injury with damage to the lungs and 68 mortality were attributed (Vandelaer, 2023).

The researchers pursued this study as a feasible research subject to examine due to its relevance in the contemporary society, the recency of occurrence which requires further research contribution and the realness of the problem as growing health concern. Upon observation of the prevalence and health circumstances regarding disposable electronic cigarettes, the researchers sought to concentratedly establish their scope in determining factors that influence the habitual consumption of disposable electronic cigarettes and its perceived health risks. Accordingly, the result of the study will serve as a contribution to the involved individuals, notably young adults, and as a basis for research endeavors.

Research Questions

This study aims to assess the young adults' perceptions toward disposable electronic cigarettes, and the accompanying health risks upon habitual consumption. Specifically, it attempts to answer the following questions:

1. What is the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1 Age
 - 1.2 Sex
 - 1.3 Educational Attainment
 - 1.4 Employment Status
 - 1.5 Weekly Allowance
 - 1.6 Monthly Salary
2. What are the factors that influence young adults to consume disposable electronic cigarettes?
 - 2.1 Interest
 - 2.2 Desirable Attributes
 - 2.3 Social Norms
 - 2.4 Knowledge
3. What are the perceived health risks of habitual consumption of disposable electronic cigarettes?
 - 3.1 Physical
 - 3.2 Psychological

3.3 sociocultural

4. Is there a significant difference in the factors that affect young adults to consume disposable electronic cigarette when grouped according to profile?
5. Is there a significant difference in the perception of respondents on health risks of the habitual consumption of disposable e-cigarette when grouped according to profile?
6. What health teachings can be disseminated to the respondents in relation to risks carried out by the habitual consumption of disposable electronic cigarettes?

METHODOLOGY

The researchers have employed a quantitative descriptive research method to assess the factors influencing the habitual consumption of disposable electronic cigarettes, and the perceived health risks. The data collection was assembled through an online survey questionnaire to derive the patterns and traits of the identified respondents. Moreover, it assessed the perception regarding the phenomenon of disposable electronic cigarettes; complementing the significance of Pender's Health Promotion Model (1982) framework.

The data gathering has been carried out in the vicinity of Quezon City, as the definitive location in assembling the respondents and optimizing the effectiveness and opportunity to acquire data. The chosen sampling design is a non-probability purposive sampling to streamline respondents based on specific criteria. Using the Google Form, a self-made 35-item questionnaire was distributed to one hundred (100) respondents, aged 18 to 26 years old, residents of Quezon City and an active consumer of the disposable electronic cigarette for more or less 3-6 months. The other demographic profile taken into account were their sex, educational attainment, employment status, weekly allowance and/or the monthly salary. An inclusion and exclusion criteria were employed for the identification of respondents displaying certain characteristics in order to achieve research objectives.

Additionally, the research adapted a 4-point Likert Scale format to interpret the gathered data, which consists of items that can be gauged according to respondents' perception. Prior to the survey distribution, the researchers undergone a validity testing to three (3) validators, all of whom confirmed that the research instrument is valid, appropriate and non-biased by evaluation. Revisions were advised for further improvements. Documents and permission letter necessary for the data collection have been managed. Thereafter, the researchers conducted a pilot testing in order to ascertain the feasibility of the study and identify weakness through a preliminary data measurement. The pilot test consisted of (10) ten respondents, which is ten percent sample size relative to its full-scale survey. After conducting the pilot testing, the researchers ran the reliability test using the data collected with the assistance of a statistician in the computation of the results. Using the Cronbach's Alpha formula, the value has indicated an internal consistency of 0.798 and with verbal interpretation of acceptable; confirming the reliability of research instrument.

The city-wide distribution of the questionnaire took place from the 8th to 10th of March 2024. Ethical considerations and provision of research context were properly addressed to the respondents beforehand. The researchers have formally sought assistance from Sangguniang Kabataan (SK) officers of the barangay to navigate the community and to introduce the potential residents. Provided that the survey questionnaire is answerable online, the researchers either handed their devices or requested that the respondents use theirs. Snack incentives were presented to the respondents as an appreciation for their efforts. After the researchers have completed conducting the survey, the gathered data were then analyzed through the application of the statistical treatment of data, such as Frequency and Percentage, Weighted Mean and Analysis of Variance, which were utilized to compute their respective research question with accompanying interpretation.

RESULTS

1. Demographic Profile of Respondents

Table 1.1 Frequency Distribution of Respondents in terms of Age

Age	Frequency	Percentage
24-26	44	44
21-23	44	44
18-20	12	12
Total	100	100%

Table 1.1 presents the frequency distribution of respondents in terms of their age. As indicated, there is an equal distribution between the age brackets 24-26 years old and 21-23 years old, constituting over 44% of the total, respectively. Followed by 18-20 years old, amounting to over 12% in the overall distribution of the respondents. These findings indicate that the majority of the respondents are between the age bracket of 21 to 26 years old.

Table 1.2 Frequency Distribution of Respondents in terms of Sex

Sex	Frequency	Percentage
Male	54	54
Female	46	46
Total	100	100%

Table 1.2 displays the frequency distribution of respondents in terms of sex. There are over fifty-four (54%) male and forty-six (46%) females who responded voluntarily in the researchers' survey questionnaire. The table interprets that there is marginal difference from the distribution of sexes, with the males being higher compared to the females.

Table 1.3 Frequency Distribution of Respondents in terms of Educational Attainment

Educational Attainment	Frequency	Percentage
Graduate Studies	2	2
College Graduate	29	29
College Undergraduate	53	53
Vocational Studies	3	3
High School Graduate	13	13
Total	100	100%

Table 1.3 presents the frequency distribution of respondents in terms of their educational attainment. Majority of the respondents are undergraduate college, accounting to over fifty three percent (53%). Following this, college graduates with over twenty-nine percent (29%). There are thirteen percent (13%) of the high school graduates and three percent (3%) of respondents have finished vocational studies. The least number of respondents were those pursuing graduate studies; constituting only two percent (2%). This implies young adult residents of Quezon City are diverse in terms of the educational attainment.

Table 1.4 Frequency Distribution of Respondents in terms of Employment Status

Status	Frequency	Percentage
Employed	35	35
Part-time	9	9
Student	47	47
Unemployed	9	9
Total	100	100%

Table 1.4 illustrates the frequency distribution of respondents in terms of employment status. Most of the respondents were students with forty-seven percent (47%), while employed respondents are over thirty-five percent (35%). Part-time and unemployed were of equal percent in sum of nine (9%). This suggested that students who are not employed made decisions to purchase disposable e-cigarettes using their allowances.

Table 1.5 Frequency Distribution of Respondents in terms of Weekly Allowance

Weekly Allowance	Frequency	Percentage
2,200-above php	26	26
1900-2100 php	2	2
1600-1800 php	4	4
1300-1500 php	12	12
1000-1200 php	16	16
700-900 php	5	5
400-600 php	10	10
100-300 php	7	7
Not Applicable	18	18
Total	100	100%

Table 1.5 shows the frequency distribution of respondents in terms of weekly allowance. The most frequent weekly allowance of respondents is 2,200php with over twenty six percent (26%). With the eighteen percent (18%), they said not applicable. Furthermore, sixteen percent (16%) of respondents have weekly allowances of 1,000-1,200php, and twelve percent (12%) with 1300-1500php. Seven percent (7%) of respondents have a weekly allowance of 100-300php, while five percent (5%) have 700-900php. Only four percent (4%) have 1600-1800php allowance, and two percent (2%) with 1900-2100php.

Table 1.6 Frequency Distribution of Respondents in terms of Monthly Salary

Monthly Salary	Frequency	Percentage
30,000 php and above	12	12
25,000-29,000 php	7	7
20,000-24000 php	5	5
15,000-19000 php	6	6
10,000-14,000 php	9	9
5,000-9,000 php	13	13
Not Applicable	48	48
Total	100	100%

Table 1.6 displays the frequency distribution of the respondents in terms of the monthly salary. Among the respondents, there is over forty eight percent (48%) that earned the most frequent response of "not applicable" when surveyed about monthly salary. This is assumed as the total number of full-time students and unemployed people who, by reasoning, do not receive a monthly salary, but still has the financial means to purchase and supply themselves with disposable electronic cigarettes. While the highest monthly earnings of more than 30,000php, 25,000–29,000php, and 20,000–24,000php went to twelve percent (12%), seven percent (7%), and five percent (5%) of respondents. Conversely, the least amount of monthly salaries is 15,000-19000php, which is six percent (6%) of the respondents. This is then followed by 10,000-14,000php, amounting to over nine percent (9%) respondents answers; and lastly, monthly salary of 5,000-9,000php belong to thirteen percent (13%) of respondents who were surveyed. Overall, the monthly salary is conditional and applicable only to respondents who are employed.

2. Factors that influence young adults to use disposable electronic cigarettes

Table 2.1 Computed Weighted Mean on the factors that influence young adults to consume disposable electronic cigarettes in terms of Interest

Items	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1. I started using disposable electronic cigarettes out of curiosity.	2.82	Agree
2. The media and public figures influenced me to use disposable electronic cigarettes.	2.48	Disagree
3. The advertisement appealed to me into using disposable electronic cigarettes.	2.44	Disagree

4. I use disposable electronic cigarettes to quit or reduce smoking.	2.77	Agree
5. I use disposable electronic cigarettes to compare its quality to tobacco cigarettes.	2.35	Disagree
Over all Computed Weighted Mean	2.57	Agree (With Impact)

Table 2.1 shows a computed weighted mean on the factors that influence young adults to consume disposable electronic cigarettes in terms of their interest. With the highest weighted mean of 2.82, this indicates that majority of the young adults have started consuming disposable electronic cigarettes mainly out of curiosity. With a weighted mean of 2.77, they have also agreed to consuming disposable electronic cigarette in order quit or reduce smoking tobacco cigarette. Moreover, the respondents disagreed that both the media and public figures have influenced them to consume disposable electronic cigarette, with a weighted mean of 2.48. Additionally, they also did not think that advertisement of the product significantly appealed to them into using disposable electronic cigarette, with a weighted mean of 2.44. The respondents disagreed that they primarily use disposable electronic cigarettes to compare its quality to the tobacco cigarettes, with a weighted mean of 2.35. As a result, the overall weighted mean is 2.57 with verbal interpretation of “agree”. Thus, interest as a factor has impact in influencing the young adults to consume disposable electronic cigarettes in satisfying their curiosity.

Table 2.2 Computed Weighted Mean on the factors that influence young adults to consume disposable electronic cigarettes in terms of Desirable Attributes

Items	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1. I use disposable electronic cigarettes because they are affordable.	2.78	Agree
2. I use disposable electronic cigarettes because they offer a variety of flavors I like.	3.36	Strongly Agree
3. I use disposable electronic cigarettes because they are customizable for a more personalized experience.	3.05	Agree
4. I use disposable electronic cigarettes because they do not smell bad.	3.38	Strongly Agree
5. I use disposable electronic cigarettes because they are accessible in product design.	3.07	Agree
Over all Computed Weighted Mean	3.11	Agree (With Impact)

Table 2.2 shows a computed weighted mean on the factors that influence young adults to consume disposable electronic cigarettes in terms of desirable attributes. With a weighted mean of 3.38, majority of the respondents use disposable electronic cigarettes because they do not smell bad. Secondly, with a weighted mean of 3.36, they use it because they offer a variety of flavors that fits their preferences in taste. Moreover, they approved that disposable electronic cigarettes are accessible in product design, such as using it in places where smoking is otherwise prohibited, and with the weighted mean of 3.07. Following this, respondents use it as they are customizable for personalized

experience and product design, with the weighted mean of 3.05. As for the lowest weighted mean of 2.78, they respondents consume disposable electronic cigarettes because they are affordable. The overall computed weighted is 3.11 with the verbal interpretation of agree. This concludes that the respondents indicated that consumption of disposable electronic cigarettes influenced by the desirable attributes has an impact.

Table 2.3 Computed Weighted Mean on the factors that influence young adults to consume disposable electronic cigarettes in terms of Social Norms

Items	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1. I use disposable electronic cigarettes because I feel pressured by my peers who engage in using it	1.97	Disagree
2. I use disposable electronic cigarettes because it is trendy and it makes me look cool.	1.99	Disagree
3. I use disposable electronic cigarettes because people close to me use them (e.g. family/friend).	2.30	Disagree
4. I feel a sense of belongingness in the vaping community.	2.24	Disagree
5. Disposable electronic cigarettes help me engage in social opportunities.	2.10	Disagree
Over all Computed Weighted Mean	2.12	Disagree (With Less Impact)

Table 2.3 illustrates the computed weighted mean on the factors that influence young adults to consume disposable electronic cigarettes in terms of social norm. With the highest weighted mean of 2.30, the respondents disagreed that they use disposable electronic cigarettes because the people close to me use them. Next, with a weighted mean of a 2.24, they don't feel sense of belongingness in the vaping community. Correspondingly, the respondents don't think that disposable electronic cigarettes help engage in social opportunities, with weighted mean of 2.10. Furthermore, the lowest computed weighted mean of 1.97 denotes to respondents disagreeing feel pressured by my peers who use disposable electronic cigarettes. Holistically, the overall computed weighted mean results to a 2.12, which designates that social norms have a lesser impact compared to the other factors.

Table 2.4 Computed Weighted Mean on the factors that influence young adults to consume disposable electronic cigarettes in terms of Knowledge

Items	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1. I am aware of the contents inside the disposable electronic cigarettes.	3.27	Strongly Agree
2. Disposable electronic cigarettes are promoted as an alternative to quit tobacco smoking	3.05	Agree
3. Disposable electronic cigarettes are healthier compared to smoking tobacco cigarettes.	2.46	Disagree

4. Disposable electronic cigarettes are less harmful to those around me compared to tobacco cigarettes	2.76	Agree
5. Disposable electronic cigarettes contain harmful chemicals that may cause long-term health effects.	3.14	Agree
Over all Computed Weighted Mean	2.94	Agree (With Impact)

Table 2.4 shows a computed weighted mean on the factors that influence young adults to consume disposable electronic cigarette in terms of knowledge. As shown, its highest weighted mean 3.27 indicates that the respondents are aware of the contents inside the disposable electronic cigarettes. With the weighted mean of 3.14, they agree that these contain harmful chemicals that may cause long-term health effect. Following this, the respondents agree that disposable electronic cigarettes are promoted as an alternative product in order to quit tobacco smoking, with the computed weighted mean of 3.05. Furthermore, with a weighted mean of 2.76, the respondents think disposable electronic cigarettes are less harmful to those around them compared to tobacco cigarettes. The lowest weighted mean of 2.46 indicates that the disposable electronic cigarettes are healthier compared to smoking tobacco cigarettes. Although they are perceived as less harmful, it still contains harmful chemicals, therefore making it an unhealthy choice. The overall computed weighted mean is 2.94; signifying that there is impact in respondents being knowledgeable about the harmful effects of consuming disposable e-cigarettes.

3. Perceived health risks of habitual consumption of disposable electronic cigarettes

Table 3.1 Computed Weighted Mean on the perceived health risks of habitual consumption of disposable electronic cigarettes in terms of Physical

Items	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1. I noticed that coughing and wheezing has been frequent since I started vaping.	2.22	Disagree
2. My throat would feel dry and itchy after vaping.	2.38	Disagree
3. I experience headaches or dizziness after vaping	2.24	Disagree
4. I feel the urge to vomit after I vape.	1.79	Disagree
5. I experience heart palpitations when I vape.	1.95	Disagree
Over all Computed Weighted Mean	2.12	Disagree (With Less Impact)

Table 3.1 presents the computed weighted mean on perceived health risks of habitual consumption of disposable electronic cigarette in terms of physical. As indicated, the highest computed weighted mean of 2.38 interprets that the respondents disagree that their throats felt dry and itchy after vaping. Additionally, with a weighted mean of 2.24, they do not experience headaches or dizziness after vaping. Thirdly, they disagree that coughing and wheezing has been frequent since they started vaping with a weighted mean of 2.22. The respondents do not experience heart palpitation when they vape with

the weighted mean of 1.95. The lowest computed weighted mean of 1.79 states that the respondents don't feel the urge to vomit after they vape. The overall computed weighted mean was 2.12, which means that physical as a perceived health risk has lesser impact.

Table 3.2 Computed Weighted Mean on the perceived health risks of habitual consumption of disposable electronic cigarettes in terms of Psychological

Items	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1. I frequently use disposable electronic cigarettes because it gives a sense of immediate satisfaction.	3.09	Agree
2. I often find myself reaching for my disposable electronic cigarette without thinking about it.	2.80	Agree
3. The urge to vape becomes stronger when I haven't done it within a few days.	2.64	Agree
4. I use disposable electronic cigarettes to relieve myself from emotional tension or stress.	3.19	Agree
5. I find myself to be easily irritated or uncomfortable when I cut vaping for a few days.	2.26	Disagree
Over all Computed Weighted Mean	2.80	Agree (With Impact)

Table 3.2 shows the computed weighted mean on perceived health risks of habitual consumption of disposable electronic cigarette in terms of psychological. The highest weighted mean of 3.19 indicates that respondents use disposable electronic cigarette to relieve themselves from emotional tension or stress. The respondents also noticed that frequently consuming disposable electronic cigarettes gave them a sense of immediate satisfaction, and with a weighted mean of 3.09.

Furthermore, they often find themselves reaching for disposable electronic cigarette without thinking about it, and has a weighted mean of 2.80 Moreover, the urge to vape becomes stronger when they have not done it within a few days, and it has a weighted mean of 2.64.

Meanwhile, the lowest weighted mean of 2.26 indicates that the respondents find themselves easily irritated or uncomfortable when they cut vaping for a few days. The overall computed weighted mean is a result of 2.80 implicating that the respondents agree that a psychological aspect has an impact.

Table 3.3 Computed Weighted Mean on the perceived health risks of habitual consumption of disposable electronic cigarettes in terms of Sociocultural

Items	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1. I often impulsively spend money on disposable electronic cigarettes.	2.52	Agree

2. Poor family relations and lack of family affection significantly impact my tendency to vape.	1.99	Disagree
3. My attitude and awareness towards vaping is influenced by the community.	2.40	Disagree
4. The availability and accessibility of disposable electronic cigarettes in the community can affect my pattern of usage.	2.70	Agree
5. The bad impression related to smoking influences me to choose vaping as the perceived safer alternative.	2.56	Agree
Over all Computed Weighted Mean	2.43	Disagree (With Less Impact)

Table 3.3 presents the computed weighted mean on perceived health risks of habitual consumption of disposable electronic cigarette in terms of sociocultural. With a weighted mean of 2.70, the respondents agree that the availability and accessibility of disposable electronic cigarettes in the community affect the pattern of usage. Next, with a weighted mean of 2.56, they agree the bad impression related to smoking influences them to choose vaping as the perceived safer alternative.

Additionally, they agree that they often impulsively spend money on disposable electronic cigarettes, with weighted mean of 2.52. With a weighted mean of 2.40, they disagreed that the attitude and awareness towards vaping is influenced by the community. The respondents do not consider that poor family relations and lack of family affection significantly impact the tendency to vape, with 1.99 weighted mean. The overall computed weighted mean is 2.43 This suggests that the sociocultural aspect in the perceived health risk of habitual vaping has a lesser impact.

4. Significant difference in the factors that influence young adults to consume disposable electronic cigarettes when grouped according to profile

Table 4.1 Test of Difference between factors that influence young adults to consume disposable electronic cigarettes when grouped according to profile in terms of Interest

Profile	Interest	Sum of Square	df	Mean Square	f	Sig-Value	Decision	Verbal Interpretation
Age	Between Groups	9.48	15	0.63	1.465	0.138	Accept	Not Significant
	Within Groups	36.27	84	0.43				
	Total	45.76	99					
Sex	Between Groups	4.05	15	0.27	1.091	0.377	Accept	Not Significant
	Within Groups	20.79	84	0.248				
	Total	24.84	99					

Educational Attainment	Between Groups	11.68	15	0.779	0.858	0.612	Accept	Not Significant
	Within Groups	76.27	84	0.908				
	Total	87.96	99					
Employment Status	Between Groups	30.11	15	2.007	2.137	0.015	Reject	Significant
	Within Groups	78.89	84	0.939				
	Total	109.00	99					

Table 4.1 determines a test of the difference between factors that influence young adults to consume disposable electronic cigarettes when grouped according to profile in terms of interest. The F-values and significant values for the following: Age 1.465 and 0.138, Sex 1.091 and 0.377, Educational Attainment 0.858 and 0.612, Employment Status 2.137 and 0.015.

Since the computed significant value for status is 0.015, which is less than a 0.05, therefore the hypothesis was decidedly rejected. This signifies that there is a significant difference between factors that influence young adults to use disposable electronic cigarettes when grouped according to status in terms of interest.

This implies based on the research results that the status of the respondents matters in their interest, although majority of the respondents have started consuming disposable electronic cigarettes out of curiosity and then later developed into habitual consumption. Meanwhile, the respondents who were employed and earned their own money can allot weekly allowance for the purchase of disposable electronic cigarettes for satisfaction.

Table 4.2 Test of Difference between factors that influence young adults to consume disposable electronic cigarettes when grouped according to profile in terms of Desirable Attributes

Profile	Desirable Attributes	Sum of Square	df	Mean Square	f	Sig-Value	Decision	Verbal Interpretation
Age	Between Groups	6.91	12	0.58	1.289	0.239	Accept	Not Significant
	Within Groups	38.85	87	0.45				
	Total	45.76	99					
Sex	Between Groups	4.46	12	0.372	1.588	0.11	Accept	Not Significant
	Within Groups	20.38	87	0.234				
	Total	24.84	99					
Educational Attainment	Between Groups	5.30	12	0.441	0.465	0.93	Accept	Not Significant

	Within Groups	82.66	87	0.95				
	Total	87.96	99					
Employment Status	Between Groups	6.71	12	0.56	0.476	0.924	Accept	Not Significant
	Within Groups	102.29	87	1.176				
	Total	109.00	99					

Table 4.2 determines the test of difference between factors that influence young adults to consume disposable electronic cigarettes when grouped according to profile in terms of desirable attributes. The F-values and significant value for the following: Age 1.289 and 0.239, Sex 1.588 and 0.11, Educational Attainment 0.465 and 0.93, Employment Status 0.476 and 0.924, respectively.

Since the computed significant value for the age, sex, educational attainment and the employment status is greater than 0.05, the decision is to accept the hypothesis which denotes that there is no significant difference between the factors that influence young adults to use disposable electronic cigarettes when grouped according to profile in terms of desirable attributes.

This implies that based on the research results, the profile of the respondents has no significant difference in regards to determining the factors that influence young adults to consume disposable electronic cigarettes in terms of the desirable attribute. Regardless of the selected demographic profile of the respondents, there is a comparable pattern that the majority of the young adults who consume disposable electronic cigarettes would share similar perceptions that the desirable attributes of the product can influence the act of vaping among young adults.

Table 4.3 Test of Difference between factors that influence young adults to consume disposable electronic cigarettes when grouped according to profile in terms of Social Norms

Profile	Social Norms	Sum of Square	df	Mean Square	f	Sig-Value	Decision	Verbal Interpretation
Age	Between Groups	4.04	14	0.29	0.588	0.867	Accept	Not Significant
	Within Groups	41.72	85	0.49				
	Total	45.76	99					
Sex	Between Groups	7.67	14	0.548	2.711	0.002	Reject	Significant
	Within Groups	17.17	85	0.202				
	Total	24.84	99					
Educational Attainment	Between Groups	10.14	14	0.724	0.791	0.676	Accept	Not Significant

	Within Groups	77.82	85	0.916				
	Total	87.96	99					
Employment Status	Between Groups	21.95	14	1.568	1.531	0.117	Accept	Not Significant
	Within Groups	87.05	85	1.024				
	Total	109.00	99					

Table 4.3 determines the test of difference between factors that influence young adults to consume disposable electronic cigarettes when grouped according to profile in terms of social norms. The F-values and significant value for the following: Age 0.588 and 0.867, Sex 2.711 and 0.002, Educational Attainment 0.791 and 0.676, Employment Status 1.531 and 0.117, respectively.

Since the computed significant value for sex is 0.002 which is less than 0.05, therefore the decision is to reject the hypothesis. Therefore, the decision signifies that there is a significant difference between the factors that influence young adults to consume disposable electronic cigarettes when grouped according to sex in terms of social norms.

This implies that male and female vapers have varying differences on why they choose to consume disposable electronic cigarettes in the context of social norms. Social identities depend on social opportunities as individuals examine and categorize people into groups and identity, which can foster and enhance their social network. As a result there is an impact on social norms with the consumption of disposable electronic cigarettes in relation to the construction of social identity.

Table 4.4 Test of Difference between factors that influence young adults to consume disposable electronic cigarettes when grouped according to profile in terms of Knowledge

Profile	Knowledge	Sum of Square	df	Mean Square	f	Sig-Value	Decision	Verbal Interpretation
Age	Between Groups	4.09	14	0.29	0.596	0.861	Accept	Not Significant
	Within Groups	41.67	85	0.49				
	Total	45.76	99					
Sex	Between Groups	4.60	14	0.328	1.379	0.181	Accept	Not Significant
	Within Groups	20.24	85	0.238				
	Total	24.84	99					
Educational Attainment	Between Groups	15.05	14	1.075	1.253	0.254	Accept	Not Significant
	Within Groups	72.91	85	0.858				

	Total	87.96	99					
Employment Status	Between Groups	20.27	14	1.448	1.387	0.177	Accept	Not Significant
	Within Groups	88.73	85	1.044				
	Total	109.00	99					

Table 4.4 determines the test of difference between factors that influence young adults to consume disposable electronic cigarettes when grouped according to profile in terms of knowledge. The F-values and significant value for the following: Age 0.596 and 0.861, Sex 1.379 and 0.181, Educational Attainment 1.253 and 0.254, Employment Status 1.387 and 0.177, respectively.

Since a computed significant value for age, sex, educational attainment and employment status is greater than 0.05 therefore the decision is to accept the hypothesis that there is no significant difference between factors that influence young adults to use disposable electronic cigarettes when grouped according to profile in terms of their knowledge.

As aforementioned, there is no disparity among the demographic profile in regards to knowledge as a factor that influences consumption of disposable electronic cigarettes for the reason that majority of the respondents largely share similar perceptions about it. Majority of them have agreed that they are knowledgeable of the contents inside the product, and that they are aware that disposable electronic cigarettes contain harmful chemicals that can potentially induce the long-term health effects from habitually vaping. Furthermore, a significant portion of the respondents have conformed to the knowledge that disposable electronic cigarettes are promoted as derivative smoking cessation aid.

5. Significant difference in the perception of respondents on health risks of the habitual consumption of disposable e-cigarettes when grouped according to profile

Table 5.1 Test of Difference between the perception of respondents on health risks of the habitual consumption of disposable e-cigarettes when grouped according to profile in terms Physical

Profile	Physical	Sum of Square	df	Mean Square	f	Sig-Value	Decision	Verbal Interpretation
Age	Between Groups	7.97	14	0.57	1.281	0.236	Accept	Not Significant
	Within Groups	37.79	85	0.45				
	Total	45.76	99					
Sex	Between Groups	3.89	14	0.278	1.127	0.347	Accept	Not Significant
	Within Groups	20.95	85	0.246				
	Total	24.84	99					

Educational Attainment	Between Groups	11.73	14	0.838	0.934	0.526	Accept	Not Significant
	Within Groups	76.23	85	0.897				
	Total	87.96	99					
Employment Status	Between Groups	21.04	14	1.503	1.452	0.148	Accept	Not Significant
	Within Groups	87.96	85	1.035				
	Total	109.00	99					

Table 5.1 determines the test of difference between the perception of respondents on health risks of the habitual consumption of disposable e-cigarettes when grouped according to profile in terms of physical. The F-values and significant value for the following: Age 1.281 and 0.236, Sex 1.127 and 0.347 Educational Attainment 0.934 and 0.526, Employment Status 1.452 and 0.148 respectively.

Since the computed significant value for age, sex, educational attainment and the employment status is greater than 0.05 therefore decision is to accept the hypothesis that there is no significant difference between the perception of respondents on health risks of the habitual consumption of disposable electronic cigarettes when grouped according to profile in terms of physical. This implies based on the result of the study that regardless of the profile at any part of the age considered, different sex male or female, no matter what degree they have finished and status in life, the respondents are aware that vaping using disposable electronic cigarettes was not beneficial to their physical state and could develop into potential health risks upon habitual consumption disposable electronic cigarettes.

Table 5.2 Test of Difference between the perception of respondents on health risks of the habitual consumption of disposable e-cigarettes when grouped according to profile in terms Psychological

Profile	Psycho-logical	Sum of Square	df	Mean Square	f	Sig-Value	Decision	Verbal Interpretation
Age	Between Groups	6.99	13	0.54	1.193	0.298	Accept	Not Significant
	Within Groups	38.77	86	0.45				
	Groups Total	45.76	99					
Sex	Between Groups	3.03	13	0.233	0.92	0.536	Accept	Not Significant
	Within Groups	21.81	86	0.254				
	Total	24.84	99					
Educational Attainment	Between Groups	10.48	13	0.806	0.895	0.562	Accept	Not Significant

	Within Groups	77.48	86	0.901				
	Total	87.96	99					
Employment Status	Between Groups	15.72	13	1.21	1.115	0.358	Accept	Not Significant
	Within Groups	93.28	86	1.085				
	Total	109.00	99					

Table 5.2 determines the test of difference between perception of respondents on health risks of habitual consumption of disposable e-cigarettes when grouped according to profile in terms of psychological. The F-values and significant value for the following: Age 1.193 and 0.298, Sex 0.92 and 0.536, Educational Attainment 0.895 and 0.562, Employment Status 1.115 and 0.358 respectively.

Since the computed significant value for the age, sex, educational attainment and the employment status is greater than 0.05, therefore the decision is to accept the hypothesis which indicates that there is no significant difference between the perceptions of the respondents on perceived health risks of habitual consumption of disposable electronic cigarettes when they grouped according to profile in terms of the psychological aspect.

This implies that there is no significant difference between the perceptions of respondents on health risks of the habitual consumption of disposable electronic cigarettes because regardless of the demographic profile of the respondents, they have all confirmed that the psychological aspect of consuming disposable electronic cigarettes can attribute to the development of health risks due to their habitual consumption.

Table 5.3 Test of Difference between the perception of respondents on health risks of the habitual consumption of disposable e-cigarettes when grouped according to profile in terms Sociocultural

Profile	Socio-cultural	Sum of Square	df	Mean Square	f	Sig-Value	Decision	Verbal Interpretation
Age	Between Groups	12.71	15	0.85	2.154	0.014	Reject	Significant
	Within Groups	33.05	84	0.39				
	Total	45.76	99					
Sex	Between Groups	5.27	15	0.351	1.508	0.121	Accept	Not Significant
	Within Groups	19.57	84	0.233				
	Total	24.84	99					
Educational Attainment	Between Groups	12.00	15	0.8	0.885	0.583	Accept	Not Significant
	Within Groups	75.95	84	0.904				
	Total							

	Total	87.96	99					
Employment Status	Between Groups	15.70	15	1.045	0.942	0.522	Accept	Not Significant
	Within Groups	93.30	84	1.111				
	Total	109.00	99					

Table 5.3 determines the test of difference between perception of respondents on health risks of the habitual consumption of disposable e-cigarettes when grouped according to profile in terms sociocultural. The F-values and significant value for the following: Age 2.154 and 0.014, Sex 1.508 and 0.121, Educational Attainment 0.885 and 0.583, Employment Status 0.942 and 0.522 respectively.

Since the computed significant value for age is 0.014 which is less than 0.05, therefore the hypothesis was rejected, which has indicated that there is a significant difference between the perception of respondents on health risks of the habitual consumption of disposable electronic cigarette when grouped according to age in terms of sociocultural.

DISCUSSION

For the first research question, most of the young adults' ages are between 24-26 and 21-23 respectively, as the predominant age range among the respondents of the study. In a recent foreign study, Tattan-Birch (2022) stated that there is an 18% increase of vapers who use disposable electronic cigarette from January 2021 to April 2022, were largely pronounced among young adults as the highest amount of demographic user. In regards to their sex, there are fifty-four (54) male and forty-six (46) female ratio of respondents indicating that the male respondents are marginally higher than the female respondents who have participated in the survey questionnaire. According to Piñeiro et al. (2016), the male respondents reported to have more positive expectancies about electronic cigarettes, including the taste, social facilitation, and energy while the females rated electronic cigarettes higher for the weight control and psychological relief benefits.

Furthermore, in regards to the educational attainment, a significant proportion of the respondents are classified as undergraduate college students with a fifty-three (53) in total. In regards to employment status, majority of the respondents are students with over forty-seven (47) partakers. In regards to the weekly allowances of the young adult respondents, the frequent weekly allowance is 2,200php and above, which indicates that majority of the respondents have the financial capacity to purchase disposable electronic cigarette. In regards to the monthly salary, the most frequent response for the monthly salary is not applicable; stating the respondents earn an irregular sum or none.

For the second research question, in terms of the interests about disposable electronic cigarettes, the respondents reflected on how it is mainly because of curiosity as to why they started to habitually vape. With an overall weighted mean of 2.82, it demonstrates to have an impact to respondents. Several studies reported that curiously is another reason

why people use e-cigarettes. As a recent invention, e-cigarettes have been of interest to people who want to try something new and unconventional (Bearss, 2018). In regards to the desirable attribute of disposable electronic cigarettes, it is thought to be desirable for consumption due to the absence of unpleasant smell. Based on the overall weighted mean of 3.38 there is impact in relation to the attractive features of the device. According to Mugharbil et al. (2023), The positive sensory experience, such as pleasant smell, various flavors and taste were most appealing aspects of disposable e-cigarettes.

However, in regards to the social norms surrounding disposable electronic cigarette, the respondents did not agree that they were influenced to vape by others, irrespective if they were closely associated with them. With an overall weighted mean of a 2.30, it is apparent this has lesser impact among respondents. In a contrasting study, Chao et al. (2019) says that individuals' behaviors are influenced by their peers and other groups to which they are associated in social network or establishment of personal social identity.

Interestingly, in regards to factors that affect young adults to use disposable electronic cigarettes in terms of knowledge, a significant portion of the respondents are aware of the constituents that are inside of the disposable electronic cigarette along with potential health risks that they might develop due to habitual vaping. This is demonstrated based in overall weighted mean of 3.27, which signifies that there is impact to the respondents.

For the third research question, in terms of the physical aspect, the respondents largely disagreed in feeling any manifestation of dryness and itchiness in their throats after vaping. The overall weighted mean of 2.12 indicates that physical has less impact in the perceived health risks of habitual consumption of disposable electronic cigarette. In a contrasting study, however, exposure to chemical concentrations found in disposable e-cigarettes has potentially been shown to stimulate irritation to the throat, as stated in a study of National Library of Medicine (2018). Also, Eissenberg (2020) states that vaping exposes the lungs to various chemicals with irritating potency in the vaporizing process.

In terms of the psychological aspect, majority of the respondents habitually consuming disposable electronic cigarettes do it to relieve themselves from the emotional tension or stress. This is based on the overall computed weighted mean of 2.80; designating that there is impact in the psychological aspect that perceives health risks from the habitual consumption of a disposable electronic cigarette. In a 2024 foreign study, a systematic review on adolescents' health perceptions on e-cigarettes scrutinized that most youth perceive vaping as a coping mechanism to manage their stress and anxiety.

Lastly, in terms of sociocultural, the respondents determine that the pattern of habitual consumption of disposable electronic cigarettes is due to both the availability and accessibility in the area. With an overall weighted mean of 2.70, the sociocultural aspect holds impact in perceived health risks as direct consequence of habitual consumption of disposable e-cigarette. Correspondingly, several studies included in the review reported that people use e-cigarettes out of convenience and affordability (Mugharbil, 2023). The convenience is due to the prevalence of product; therefore, it becomes easily accessible

and available in various communities, and the affordability influences the sociocultural aspect by means of unhealthy impulsion to purchasing disposable electronic cigarettes.

For the fourth research question, the difference between factors that influence young adults to use disposable electronic cigarettes when grouped according to profile. In terms of interest, the F-values and significant values were determined through the following: Age 1.465 and 0.138, Sex 1.091 and 0.377, Educational Attainment 0.858 and 0.612, Employment Status with 2.137 and 0.015. According to Mullins (2022), the promotion for electronic cigarettes purposely target the youth population in commercials by linking vaping with the intriguing ideals, like happiness, friendship and success. They are commonly marketed by stating the advantage of e-cigarettes over normal cigarette.

Meanwhile, in terms of desirable attributes, the F-values and significant value for the following are: Age 1.289 and 0.239, Sex 1.588 and 0.11, Educational Attainment 0.465 and 0.93, Status 0.476 and 0.924 respectively. The sensory experiences of vaping were desirable qualities, such as smell and flavor, are found to be prominent roles to motivate the use of vaping products. As confirmed by similar studies, a major determinant to use electronic cigarette was the provision of pleasant sensory experience (Lee et al., 2017). In terms of social norms, the F-values and significant value for the following: Age 0.588 and 0.867, Sex 2.711 and 0.002, Educational Attainment 0.791 and 0.676, Employment Status 1.531 and 0.117 respectively. Blank and Hoek (2022) supplement the impact of social norms with disposable electronic cigarettes in relation to construction of social identity. Social identities depend on social opportunities as individuals examine and categorize people into groups and identify among groups which foster and enhance self-esteem. Youth compare groups to refine or strengthen affiliation and social identity.

In terms of knowledge, the F-values and significant value for the following: Age 0.596 and 0.861, Sex 1.379 and 0.181, Educational Attainment 1.253 and 0.254, Employment Status 1.387 and 0.177 respectively. In a similar study, Popova (2020) has explained that it is partly because disposable e-cigarette manufacturers are not always transparent in which chemicals or drugs have been incorporated within the product. The lack of transparency in ingredients resulted in young adults becoming susceptible to habitual consumption of disposable electronic cigarette due to misconstrued knowledge.

The test of difference between the perception of respondents on health risks of the habitual consumption of disposable e-cigarettes when grouped according to profile in terms physical. The F-values and significant value for the following: Age 1.281 and 0.236, Sex 1.127 and 0.347, Educational Attainment 0.934 and 0.526, Employment Status 1.452 and 0.148 respectively. Maryam & Barthelemy (2020) states that there is a worrying increase among young adults who perceive e-cigarettes as a new and safe trend and part of healthy life. Thus, leading to the negligent acts with electronic cigarette which can be adapted up by young adults without careful health-related considerations.

In terms psychological, the F-values and significant value for the following: Age 1.193 and 0.298, Sex 0.92 and 0.536, Educational Attainment 0.895 and 0.562, Employment Status 1.115 and 0.358 respectively. Cabral (2022) stated in his current study that aims to

examine rates of cigarette smoking, e-cigarette use, dual usage, and cannabis vaping during the early months of the pandemic. In the study, it determines the influence of intentions to use electronic cigarette in relieving psychological distress (i.e., anxiety, depression, loneliness or stress) on vaping behaviors among young adults respondents.

In terms of the sociocultural aspect, the F-values and significant value for the following: Age 2.154 and 0.014, Sex 1.508 and 0.121, Educational Attainment 0.885 and 0.583, Employment Status 0.942 and 0.522 respectively. Societal interpretations transformed vaping into an accessory lifestyle choice, influenced by consumerism culture and trend. Furthermore, social representations of electronic cigarettes impact its acceptability with varying perceptions; highlighting the role of social influence in shaping attitudes towards vaping, and the prevalence based on its availability and accessibility (Davidson, 2023).

Conclusions

The young adults, aged 21-26, are predominant age ranges in consumers of disposable electronic cigarette, with relatively higher usage in male respondents. Most of the young adult vapers are undergraduate college students with a weekly allowance of 2,200php above; signifying they have the financial capacity to buy disposable electronic cigarette. Moreover, the initial interest of consuming disposable electronic cigarettes was primarily due to curiosity and desirable attribute of absence of any unpleasant smell encouraged further inclination to habitually consume the product. The young adults autonomously decided to engage in the habit of vaping, thus they have not been influenced by others. Accordingly, they were also aware of the contents that are inside disposable electronic cigarette, along with health risks they can possibly develop. Despite their awareness, however, they still continued to habitually consume the disposable electronic cigarettes.

The physical health risks were not apparent among the respondents in regards to their habitual consumption, but they found it significantly effective in relieving psychological demands, such as emotional tension or stress. Furthermore, due to the availability and accessibility of disposable electronic cigarettes in their communities, this has greatly motivated the young adult respondents in persisting with their habitual pattern of vaping.

A significant difference is confirmed between factors that influence young adults to use disposable electronic cigarettes when grouped according to status in terms of interest. Although most of the respondents started using disposable electronic cigarettes out of curiosity and became a habit, the employment status of respondents matters in interest because it varies how a student or employee consumes disposable electronic cigarettes.

Also, there is a significant difference between factors that influence young adults to use disposable electronic cigarette when grouped according to sex in terms of social norms. Males consider more positive expectancies about electronic cigarettes, including taste, social facilitation or energy, while females for the weight control and psychological relief. There is a significant difference between the perception of respondents on health risks of the habitual consumption of disposable e-cigarettes when grouped according to age in

terms of sociocultural due to differences in attitudes and awareness towards vaping, and because of the accessibility and availability of disposable e-cigarette in community.

Dissemination of health teachings, particularly the reorientation of chemical properties of disposable electronic cigarette and the health consequence of habitual consumption, adaptation of healthy diversions and partaking in health-oriented programs, are effective interventions which corresponds to the Health Promotion Model of Pender (1982) as a holistic guide for the young adults to avoid developing health risk due to habitual vaping.

Recommendations

After the analysis of findings and formulation of a conclusion, the following suggestions are presented to enhance the research in terms of data, design, and implementation.

1. In accordance to Health Promotion Model, autonomous health-seeking practices should be integrated into the health teaching. Young adults should be oriented of the chemical properties inside disposable electronic cigarettes, and the imminent health consequences of habitual consumption. Additionally, they should consider engagement in healthier diversion or activity which do not impose detrimental risk to their health, and should be encouraged to partake in health-oriented programs.
2. The government should intensify their effort to strictly regulate the manufacture of disposable electronic cigarettes and their legal distribution to the market, so that observation of toxic chemical property is strictly assessed with vigilant inspection.
3. For the manufacturers of disposable electronic cigarettes, product advertisement should incorporate precautionary health measures and avoid promotion of vague health claim. Transparency of its content, especially chemicals, is recommended.
4. For the community, proposals of seminars and programs about the prevalence of disposable electronic cigarettes among the Filipino youth should be conducted to raise awareness on the growing health concern due to various influential factors that encourage habitual consumption of the device and its perceived health risks.
5. Due to the study's limitations, future researchers should expand their study on a larger scope in terms of sample size, research locale, and the age inclusion in an effort to maximize the results based on varied size and age range of respondents.
6. Future researchers can compare the impact of disposable electronic cigarettes to other variants under Electronic Nicotine Delivery System (ENDS) to determine its level of influence to a targeted demographic relative to other e-cigarette variants.
7. Provided that this study is centralized on disposable electronic cigarette, this can serve as a foundation for future studies which corresponds to the subject or it can be a baseline for the comparative studies that can utilize the data for comparison.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

In accordance with the ethical consideration of the study, the researchers have adhered to appropriate standards of conduct and principle in order to safeguard the well-being of the respondents and ensure the integrity of research. Moreover, the researchers did not force respondents to be surveyed as they were informed beforehand that participation is voluntary and that withdrawal was readily a choice should they decide not to participate.

The necessary document and permission letter were secured before the initiation of the survey. Confidentiality was ensured, and data were strictly used for academic purposes. The conclusion derived from the results is assured to be clear of any data manipulation.

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